

Eco-Credentials in the Fashion and Textile Industry Assessment and Evaluation:

A Review of Eco-Credentials, their Strengths and Weaknesses,
and Recommendations for Improvement

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Executive Summary

The negative environmental impacts caused by the textile and fashion industry (TFI) operations are increasing despite actions to “bend-the-curve” of the TFI’s current trajectory towards sustainability. Ecolabels play a critical role in shaping sustainability practices within TFI, by setting benchmarks for environmental attributes, promoting transparency, and fostering lifecycle and value chain consideration.

Several challenges persist to increase the effectiveness of ecolabels.

While ecolabels have potential to help aligning environmental priorities and guide consumer purchasing decisions their lack of scientific integration, inconsistent environmental attribute selection, and vague criteria hinder effective cross-label comparisons and limit consumer comprehension. Additionally, transparency gaps in certification processes, particularly regarding certifier ownership structures, contribute to consumer distrust.

Four key dimensions to reduce consumer uncertainty and enhance ecolabel effectiveness.

Our aim is to provide insights to improve the transparency, comparability, and trustworthiness of ecolabels within the TFI. The four key dimensions we present are scientifically set to enhance the effectiveness of ecolabels in signalling environmental performance and guiding both consumer behaviour and firms’ strategies toward sustainability.

- **Standardisation of Environmental Attributes.** Ecolabels vary widely in terms of the environmental attributes they assess, such as carbon footprint, water usage, and biodiversity. This lack of uniformity obstructs comparisons between ecolabels. Standardising the assessment of key environmental attributes at a minimum, will provide clear, comparable information across labels.
- **Improved Transparency in Monitoring and Certification Processes.** Third-party verification ensures the robustness of sustainability claims and fosters trust among consumers. This includes transparency in the verification process and clarity on the relationship between the company and the certifying organisation. It also helps to clarify the roles of the certifier – who is responsible for issuing the ecolabel – and the verifier – whose role it is to audit or assess the data.
- **Lifecycle and Value Chain Considerations.** Ecolabels in the TFI cover different value chain scopes. Transparency in the verified value chain stages, along with clarity on which part of a garment has been certified –whether it is the fibres or the final product – provides consumers a more accurate understanding of the product's environmental impact.
- **Effective Communication of Ecolabel Information.** Ecolabels target two different audiences, Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B). Understanding how the information about ecolabels is conveyed to diverse stakeholders and audiences is crucial for the effectiveness of an ecolabel.

Key Strengths and Weaknesses of Ecolabels.

Ecolabels’ strength is that they set benchmarks for environmental attributes, helping stakeholders align on key environmental priorities. Rigorous certification processes, particularly third-party verification, contribute to transparency and trust in sustainability standards. Ecolabels cover various lifecycle stages, providing a comprehensive view of environmental impacts. Their weaknesses include inconsistent environmental attributes and a lack of a systems-based approach, which hinder the development of standardized assessment methods. Vague language and insufficient transparency undermine the educational value of ecolabels, leading to consumer distrust. Additionally, inconsistent and complex communication strategies hinder consumer understanding and informed decision-making.

Four recommendations to strengthen the effectiveness of ecolabels in the TFI.

By adopting a systems and scientific approach, standardizing criteria, and enhancing communication strategies ecolabels can better serve as credible, accessible tools for promoting sustainable practices and guiding consumers and firms alike toward more environmentally responsible choices within the textile and fashion industry. Our four recommendations below, help address these goals by ensuring consistency in environmental standards, adopting a systems-based approach, strengthening ecolabel standards beyond third-party verification, and improving communication strategies.

1. Ensure consistency in environmental standards.

Inconsistencies in environmental standards and criteria across different ecolabels pose a significant challenge, making it difficult for consumers to compare garment accurately. Ecolabels need to adopt standardised criteria and align with international sustainability frameworks, such as those set out by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This will allow for more reliable cross-label comparisons, enhance their credibility, and help prevent the proliferation of misleading or vague claims.

2. Adopt a more systems-based approach.

One of the key weaknesses of current ecolabels is the lack of a comprehensive, systems-based approach to sustainability. Rather than focusing on isolated environmental attributes ecolabels should take a systems approach that considers the interconnections between various environmental impacts. By using a lifecycle approach that incorporates multiple environmental dimensions, ecolabels can more accurately reflect the true sustainability of textile fashion, reducing the risk of "cherry-picking" criteria and promoting a more complete and balanced view of sustainability. Importantly, adopting a system approach also applies to the value chain scopes. Certifying merely a narrow part of the value chain overlooks significant environmental impacts occurring earlier in the lifecycle, failing to capture the extent of the final products impacts that can result in suboptimal sustainability outcomes.

3. Strengthen ecolabel standards beyond third-party verification.

While third-party verification of ecolabels in the TFI provides credibility and trust, it is not enough to ensure comprehensive sustainability practices. Current ecolabel standards focus on relative improvements rather than absolute sustainability, failing to account for the global environmental impact of large-scale production and missing the systemic understanding needed for meaningful environmental action. The varying standards, criteria, and reassessment schemes of ecolabels contribute to vagueness, lack of transparency and even slipperiness in communications on what has been assessed and verified. Consequently, a component or product certified by one ecolabel might not meet other ecolabels criteria, leading to gaps in sustainability practices. The transparency issues in certification processes and criteria also obstructs verifying ecolabel claims, diminishing the value of third-party verification. Even when using third-party verification, firms may still engage in greenwashing as they can meet the minimum certification requirements without making substantial changes to their practices. This undermines the whole purpose of ecolabels.

4. Improve communication strategies.

A major barrier to the effectiveness of ecolabels is the communication gap between certification bodies, firms, and consumers. Ecolabels suffer from either oversimplified messaging or overly technical language, both of which hinder their accessibility. On one hand, some ecolabels reduce complex sustainability issues to simplistic claims that at best fail to convey the depth of the environmental impacts or criteria they cover, or present borderline greenwashing messages. On the other hand, some labels use dense, technical language that is difficult for the average consumer to interpret, creating confusion and reducing the label's effectiveness in guiding informed decisions. To address this, ecolabels need to strike a balance between accessibility and accuracy. Communication should be clear, simple, and consumer-friendly, while still conveying the necessary detail about the sustainability claims.

Glossary

Concept	Description
Certifier	The entity responsible for issuing the ecolabel and also that sets the standards, criteria, and procedures for certification.
Eco-credentials	Standards that help firms enhance their environmental performance.
Ecolabels	Voluntary self-regulation tools that indicate products (or processes) as environmentally preferable based on life-cycle considerations. Ecolabels signify that the product meets stated environmental and social criteria, thereby claiming it has less negative environmental (and/or social) impacts compared to similar products. Ecolabels with independently verified, credible, non-misleading information about the environmental impacts of products, differentiates products in the marketplace with an aim to promote more sustainable production and consumption practices.
Sustainability	Defined by policy in accordance with the Brundtland Report (WCED 1987). The report describes sustainable development as a concept that aims to promote "harmony among human beings and harmony between nature and humans". This wording reflects a broad policy and scholarly consensus that shapes the operating space for firms.
Sustainability Standard	Voluntary governance tools that organizations use to manage their environmental, social, and ethical impacts, providing guidelines to meet criteria such as fair labour practices, supply chain transparency, resource efficiency, and environmental impact. For example, Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), a framework for sustainability reporting.
Value chain	A series of business activities that generate value in the company to achieve a competitive advantage. Often begins with extraction and production of resources and stops with consumer sales or end-of-life.
Supply chain	The integration of all the activities involved in the creation and distribution of a product, from raw material sourcing to final consumer delivery.
Verifier	The entity responsible for auditing or assessing whether a component, product or process, meets the established criteria or eco-credentials of the certification.

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1. The Environmental Impact of the Textile and Fashion Industry

The textile and fashion industry (TFI) exerts a negative impact upon the environment during both its production and consumption phases. Specifically, regarding greenhouse gas emissions, it is estimated that in 2020, the production of textile products consumed in the EU resulted in 121 million tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂eq) emissions overall, equating to 270 kg CO₂eq per person (ETC/CE, 2022; ETC/WMGE, 2019). As a result, there is growing pressure on firms within the TFI to take responsibility for their environmental impact. In addition to, and in some cases a pre-emptive measure to comply with, mandatory regulations (Boström and Klintman, 2008; Gertz, 2005), voluntary measures such as eco-credential standards have proliferated in recent years as part of the industry's response to these concerns.

1.1. Background and importance of eco-credential standards

Eco-credentials encompass standards such as ISO standards and ecolabels. While ecolabels standardise products in the marketplace, ISO standards focus on standardising a firm's internal procedures (Darnall et al., 2018). Both aim to enhance the environmental performance of firms' activities, either by targeting specific products or inputs, as ecolabels do, or by concentrating on firms' operational processes, as is the case with ISO standards. Eco-credentials are important as they enable firms to signal their enhanced environmental commitment to key stakeholders, including the government, suppliers, and customers.

Although the primary goal of eco-credentials is to provide external stakeholders with clear information about a firm's environmental impact, their effectiveness is questionable. This problem stems partly from the proliferation of eco-credentials available. According to Ecolabel Index (2024) there are over 456 eco-credentials globally across 25 industries, with at least 107 specific to the TFI. This proliferation obscures the process for firms trying to select the most suitable eco-credential. According to Ranasinghe and Jayasooriya (2021), there are no systematic methods to identify the optimal ecolabel for a specific garment product. As a result, external stakeholders, such as consumers and regulators, face confusion, as they are unable to verify environmental performance across different eco-credentials, making it difficult to assess a firm's or product's environmental impact.

1.2. Our perspective and justification of its importance

In this study, we focus primarily on ecolabels due to the unique characteristics of the TFI, namely its consumer-facing nature and reliance on a global supply chain (Common Objective, 2018; House of Commons, 2019; McKinsey & Company, 2023; OEC, 2022). First, the fashion industry is visible to consumers, who increasingly value sustainability in their purchasing decisions. Ecolabels can play a critical role in this context as they serve as a signal of a product's environmental credentials, guiding consumers toward more eco-friendly choices. Second, the TFI operates across global supply chains, with significant environmental impacts, particularly in countries in the Global South (Anguelov, 2015; Niinimäki et al., 2020). For instance, it is estimated that while textiles consumed in Europe generate 121 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions, almost 75% of these emissions are released outside Europe, primarily in Asia (ETC/WMGE, 2019). Ecolabels focus on the product-specific environmental impact,

but not all cover the entire value chain, which refers to the series of activities from resource extraction to consumer sales that firms manage to generate value and achieve competitive advantage (Porter, 1985). Some ecolabels assess the environmental impact from cradle-to-gate (from raw material extraction to the factory gate), others from gate-to-gate (covering specific stages within the production process), while some encompass the entire cradle-to-grave lifecycle (including production, usage, and disposal). This variability in scope affects their suitability for assessing the overall environmental footprint, including emissions generated in production abroad. In contrast, environmental standards focus primarily on the internal operations of firms, assessing the environmental management systems rather than the specific products. This approach may overlook the broader environmental impact of outsourced or imported products, which is a major concern in industries like fashion, where most production occurs outside the country of consumption. Therefore, ecolabels provide a more comprehensive assessment of a product's environmental footprint, which is crucial in a globalised supply chain context.

However, ecolabels vary across several dimensions. Previous research highlights two key factors: the type of sponsor and the monitoring process (Darnall et al., 2018). Regarding the type of sponsor, ecolabels can be sponsored by governments, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), or business associations, each offering different levels of credibility. The monitoring process varies; some ecolabels are internally monitored through self-assessment, while others use second-party verification (monitored by the sponsor) or third-party verification (monitored by an independent party), which provides the topmost level of credibility ("Global Ecolabelling Network," 2019). These distinctions impact how ecolabels signal a firm's environmental commitment and how much trust stakeholders place in them.

Building on this literature, we contribute by expanding the dimensions for assessing ecolabels in the TFI by incorporating three additional factors:

- ***Environmental Attributes:*** Ecolabels focus on different aspects of environmental impact, such as carbon emissions, biodiversity, or water use etc. (Boström and Klintman, 2008; Gertz, 2005; Ranasinghe and Jayasooriya, 2021; Ziyeh and Cinelli, 2023). These differences complicate direct comparisons between ecolabels. Therefore, we will disentangle ecolabels based on their environmental attributes.
- ***Value-Chain Scope:*** Ecolabels can either cover the Cradle-to-Grave life cycle of a product, promoting circularity, or have a narrower focus. We will identify the value-chain scope of ecolabels. These expanded dimensions will help us systematically assess the most appropriate ecolabels for the TFI and improve transparency and trust among stakeholders.
- ***Communication channel:*** Ecolabels target two different audiences, Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B). We identify which audience the ecolabels target. This understanding is essential, as information about ecolabels is effectively conveyed differently to diverse stakeholders. This, in turn, affects stakeholder and consumer decisions, supporting the potential of ecolabels to drive more sustainable choices and practices across the textile and fashion industry.

2. Literature and Conceptual Framework

A unique aspect of this study on ecolabels is the comprehensive evaluation it provides of all so-called ecolabels on textiles listed in the Ecolabel Index. Unlike previous literature, which often refers to the Ecolabel Index in a generalised manner (Castka and Corbett, 2016; Darnall et al., 2018; Henninger, 2015; Ranasinghe and Jayasooriya, 2021), our study undertakes a thorough assessment of each ecolabel within this database. This systematic approach, where we analyse the credentials associated with each ecolabel, provides a detailed understanding of the diversity, criteria, and credibility of the ecolabels currently in use.

In this study, we seek to systematically assess the ecolabels within the TFI to gain a better understanding of the most appropriate ecolabels for firms in the industry. By addressing the lack of research on ecolabels in the TFI (Ranasinghe and Jayasooriya, 2021), this assessment aims to enable firms to make optimal decisions in choosing among hundreds of ecolabels. Furthermore, this research will enhance transparency within the TFI by providing a systematic comparison of ecolabels, allowing regulators, producers, and consumers to decipher the environmental footprint of TFI products. One empirical contribution is that we identified a list of ecolabels in the fashion and textile industry that address environmental issues comprehensively, thus offering a foundation for future improvements in ecolabel certification processes.

2.1. Literature Review: Ecolabels and their application in the Textile Fashion Industry

Understanding Ecolabels: Purpose, Definition and Challenges

The literature offers various definitions of ecolabels, emphasising different common aspects. Visually, ecolabels are often recognized as symbols, logos, or graphics indicating a product's environmental impact, a form of 'green claim' aimed at guiding consumer choices (GOV.UK, 2022; Henninger, 2015). These symbols or signs are awarded to products and services that demonstrate environmentally friendly attributes compared to their competition, with the overall goal of stimulating market-driven environmental improvement through verified and accurate information (Henninger, 2015).

Ecolabels are typically voluntary tags certifying products as sustainable by listing their full credentials (Fashion United, 2021). The Global Ecolabelling Network describes ecolabelling as a voluntary method of product environmental performance labelling, meant to inform consumers about the positive environmental aspects of a product (Global Ecolabelling Network, 2024).

From a consumer-facing perspective, ecolabels are tools that support decision-making regarding environmentally significant products, helping consumers to distinguish environmentally beneficial choices from conventional ones through standardised symbols and criteria (Thøgersen et al., 2010; Darnall et al., 2023). They provide a means for consumers to identify and choose products that meet sustainability criteria, thus influencing consumer behaviour towards more eco-friendly options (Boström & Micheletti, 2016).

Ecolabels are also defined by their environmental credentials, identifying products or services with overall environmental preference based on life-cycle considerations (Ranasinghe & Jayasooriya, 2021). For example, the EU Ecolabel offers a reliable way to identify high-performing environmentally friendly textile and footwear products available on the European market (European Commission, 2024).

In a firm's context, ecolabels enable firms to quickly convey to stakeholders that their products meet certain sustainability standards, serving as a valuable tool for market differentiation (KPMR, 2023). These labels indicate overall environmental preferability within a product category, awarded through independent, voluntary programs (ISO 14020:2022(E)).

Moreover, ecolabels are linked to international sustainability standards which focus on standardising firms' internal sustainability procedures to promote greater environmental responsibility through risk management and third-party audits (Darnall et al., 2023).

Legally, ecolabels can be protected labels warranting that a product complies with predetermined environmental and sometimes social criteria. They act as market-driven environmental policy instruments promoting the development of environmentally preferable goods and services through consumer choice (Hanks et al., 2003; Naumann, 2001).

Based on the above we define ecolabels as:

voluntary self-regulation tools that indicate products (or processes) as environmentally preferable based on life-cycle considerations. Ecolabels signifies that the product meets stated environmental and social criteria, thereby claiming it has less negative environmental (and/or social) impacts compared to similar products. Ecolabels with independently verified, credible, non-misleading information about the environmental impacts of products, differentiates products in the marketplace with an aim to promote more sustainable production and consumption practices.

The key difference between a third-party-, a self-declared ecolabel and a LCA is that an LCA is primarily an internal sustainability practice used to assess and improve the environmental impact of products or processes within a firm. It is not necessarily externally visible unless the results are published. By contrast, all ecolabels are intended to be visible to external stakeholders. A third-party ecolabel is based on verified LCA data. A self-declared ecolabel, on the other hand, is issued by the firm without third-party verification and communicates certain environmental claims directly to consumers and external stakeholders.

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) classifies ecolabels into different types. ISO 14024:2018, Type I labels (ISO, 2019), such as the EU Ecolabel or Blue Angel, are awarded based on compliance with a set of predefined sustainability criteria and are independently verified. Type II labels (ISO 14021) are self-declared claims by manufacturers, while Type III labels present quantified environmental data without a specific assessment on sustainability (ISO 14025) 14024:2018. While Type I-II-III outline various aspects of the principles and procedures for environmental labels and

declarations, and self-declared environmental claims, they do not specify which environmental aspects must be included in a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Instead, it is required that criteria for ecolabelling programs be based on scientifically sound LCA considerations, covering multiple environmental aspects relevant to the product category. The standards ensure that significant environmental impacts are identified and addressed but leaves the specific aspects to be determined by individual ecolabelling programs based on their methodologies and the product's environmental impact (ISO 14024:18; 14020:2023). By providing an environmental signal to consumers, ecolabels aim to address information asymmetries between producers and consumers regarding the environmental impact of products (Darnall et al., 2018; Shen and Saijo, 2009).

Ecolabels serve an important function by enabling consumers to make more informed and environmentally friendly choices (Atkinson and Rosenthal, 2014). In industries like textiles and fashion, which have global and complex supply chains and significant environmental impacts, ecolabels can provide transparency about a product's environmental footprint (Niinimäki et al., 2020). With consumers increasingly demanding more sustainable products, ecolabels have become essential for differentiating eco-friendly products from traditional ones (Darnall et al., 2018). This distinction potentially not only encourages sustainable consumption but also fosters competition among firms to improve their environmental performance.

Producers and consumers alike experience uncertainty due to the large number and diversity of ecolabels available (Boström and Micheletti, 2016). For example, the Ecolabel Index lists over 100 ecolabels related to the textile and fashion industry, each with varying criteria and levels of credibility (Ecolabel Index, 2024). This proliferation of labels creates confusion, making it difficult for producers to choose the most appropriate label for their products and complicating consumer decision-making. Previous studies have shown that the absence of standardised assessment methods across ecolabels exacerbates this uncertainty, leading to consumer distrust and undermining the credibility of ecolabels (Henninger, 2015; Žurga and Tavčer, 2014). Furthermore, different ecolabels assess various sustainability aspects, such as carbon emissions, water use, or labour conditions, further adding to consumer confusion (Liu et al., 2021). This lack of uniformity can ultimately reduce the effectiveness of ecolabels in promoting sustainability within the TFI.

Contextualising ecolabels for textile fashion

Today the TFI is considered as one of the most environmentally harmful sectors, contributing to approximately 3% to 10% of global carbon emissions, alongside freshwater use and pollution (Anguelov, 2015; Niinimäki et al., 2020; Peters et al., 2021). There is a consensus amongst academics, policy-makers, textile and fashion industry stakeholders and consumers that there is an urgent need for action to “bend-the-curve” of the TFI's current trajectory towards sustainability (Cornell et al., 2021; EMF, 2017; European Commission, 2022; European Environmental Agency EEA, 2020; House of Commons, 2019; Palm, 2023a; Peters et al., 2021).

Historical Context to the Scrutiny in the Fashion Textile Industry

The scrutiny surrounding the fashion textile industry (TFI) is deeply rooted in its historical context, dating back to the dawn of the Industrial Revolution. From the 1850s, the environmental impact of the

industry began to attract attention, with reports of salinized soil caused by the intensive irrigation of cotton fields, highlighting the ecological toll of large-scale textile production (Beckert, 2015). Social concerns soon followed, as sweatshops emerged in the late 1800s in Great Britain, notorious for their hazardous working conditions, extremely low wages, and gruelling hours (Powell, 2014)

This foundational scrutiny has shaped the industry's trajectory, reflecting a longstanding tension between industrial advancement and ethical considerations. To fully comprehend the challenges faced by the TFI in adopting ecolabels, it is essential to consider the historical and cultural context.

Key events, such as the 1990s "Nike scandal," further intensified public scrutiny (Doorey, 2011; Hart, 2017). This moment marked the rise of political consumerism, where consumer purchasing power became a tool for expressing values and demanding transparency. Textile fashion firms became aware of the effects media reporting had on impacting consumer behaviour and decades later Nike "[...] *still suffers from the historical references used by traditional and online media in their coverage of "sweatshop" conditions [...]*" (Hart, 2017, p. 4). Since then, public awareness and demand for accountability have driven brands to respond to mounting pressures for more ethical and environmentally sound practices.

In response to these concerns, Oeko-Tex in 1994, launched the first ecolabel for textiles in 1994, targeting harmful chemicals and substances (Gardiner and Trollip, 1996). The same year Fairtrade (2019) launched what is considered to be the first ecolabel focusing on the working conditions. Since then, ecolabels have grown increasingly important in signalling sustainability within the TFI.

The Impact of De-Traditionalization and Shifting Consumer Behaviour

The Nike-scandal in the 1990s coincides with the rise in *de-traditionalization* which refers to a cultural shift which includes "*the emergence of new historical possibilities for individual self-formation and for a development of the private sphere under conditions of relative social security and of the declining authority of tradition*" (Beck and Beck, 2009, p. 98). This transformation encouraged fashion consumers to be more critical of the ethical implications of their purchases, fostering a demand for information on production ethics (Boström and Micheletti, 2016). The 1990s also saw the rise of the internet and social media, increasing reliance on influencer opinions and consumer reviews over traditional norms or brand loyalty.

While this ethical awareness has driven consumer interest in sustainable and ethically labelled products, it also coincided with the rise of fast fashion – affordable, frequently updated apparel offered by large retail chains (Entwistle, 2015; Palm, 2023a; Zamani, 2014). Despite the positive impact of increased ethical awareness, fast fashion remains a major contributor to global environmental issues associated with the TFI. This ongoing tension between ethical awareness and the demand for low-cost, fast-moving fashion products illustrates the unique challenges the TFI faces in implementing sustainable practices. Although ecolabels provide consumers with valuable information about the environmental and social impacts of their purchases, the widespread adoption of these labels within this industry is complex and multifaceted.

On the one hand, ecolabels aim to enhance transparency and promote sustainable practices by empowering consumers to make informed choices (Lou and Xu, 2024; Pedersen and Neergaard, 2006). As such, ecolabels have potential to “*reduce consumer uncertainty about the validity of their green purchases*” (Darnall et al., 2018, p. 954). However, the TFI must grapple with a vast global supply chain, where ensuring compliance with ecolabel standards across multiple production stages presents a considerable hurdle. Additionally, the rapid pace of fashion trends and the relentless demand for inexpensive, readily available clothing often clash with the more measured, costly processes required to meet ecolabel criteria.

The dual influence of political consumerism and the rise of fast fashion has further amplified these challenges. As consumers increasingly demand accountability, ecolabels have become more significant, symbolising a commitment to ethical standards. Nonetheless, the very nature of fast fashion—emphasising speed, cost-efficiency, and mass production—often directly opposes the sustainability ethos that ecolabels promote.

Ultimately, for the TFI to fully embrace ecolabels and other sustainable practices, there must be a shift not only within industry operations but also in consumer attitudes and expectations. Balancing these opposing forces will be crucial for the industry as it moves towards a more transparent and environmentally responsible future.

Box 1. Focus and Evolution of Cotton Ecolabels in the Textile Industry

It is noteworthy that 9 out of 13 “components” ecolabels focus specifically on cotton, with 8 certifying organic cotton, while none target synthetic fibres. This emphasis on cotton contrasts sharply with the actual fibre composition in fashion: cotton accounts for approximately 25% of textile fibres used, whereas polyester represents about 50% (Niinimäki et al., 2020). Organic cotton makes up only a small fraction of the market, around 1% of total cotton production (1.4% according to Textile Exchange, 2022).

One factor contributing to this uneven distribution of ecolabels is cotton’s history of commodity labelling. Cotton was the first fibre to be branded with the introduction of the ‘Seal of Cotton’ in 1973. This initiative aimed to recapture market share lost in the 1960s to synthetic fibres (Cotton Incorporated, 2024; Jacobson and Smith, 2001). By 1980, the ‘Seal of Cotton’ had become widely recognised, with 57% of Americans associating it with quality, comfort, and value, and cotton’s market share surged to nearly 40% (Jacobson and Smith, 2001, p. 165). This pioneering branding approach set a precedent for the future of commodity-focused labels, influencing subsequent certifications and ecolabels in agriculture and textiles.

Ecolabels for organic fibres provide robust traceability and promote sustainable agriculture, yet they are costly for all parties involved—from farmers to retailers. Ecolabels for organically cultivated fibres, start certification at the resource extraction phase. These labels require verification that organic practices are followed from initial farming stages. The certification accompanies the product throughout its lifecycle, maintaining its organic status across each stage of the value chain, ensuring adherence to organic standards from cultivation to consumer. In contrast, ecolabels using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodologies evaluate a product’s environmental impact after production, analysing its entire lifecycle from manufacture and use to disposal. This approach assesses compliance with environmental criteria across each phase of the product’s lifecycle. Both verification approaches have distinct strengths and challenges.

Due to the complexity of global fibre trading in the fashion value chain (OEC 2022), verification can be challenging to manage (Ranasinghe and Jayasooriya, 2021). LCA-based ecolabels, meanwhile, offer a broad assessment of environmental impact across a product's lifecycle but are resource-intensive and demand well-informed, engaged consumers for effectiveness.

Source: Authors

Exploring Consumer Behaviour, Beliefs, and Attitudes

The past decade has seen a substantial increase in research on consumer behaviour in the textile fashion industry, especially concerning sustainability-related beliefs and attitudes. In line with the concept of *de-traditionalization*, studies indicate that consumers are becoming more conscious of the impacts of their consumption choices, prompting a growing demand for information to support ethical decision-making (Boström and Micheletti, 2016; Darnall et al., 2018; Ranasinghe and Jayasooriya, 2021; Thøgersen et al., 2010). However, there is a contrasting perspective suggesting that many textile fashion consumers lack sufficient knowledge or interest in sustainability issues (Palomo-Lovinski and Hahn, 2020). Even among consumers who express eco-minded intentions, research shows that few consistently act on these preferences. Darnall with colleagues (2018, p. 953) state that that for ecolabels in general “*only one in five eco-minded consumers report acting on their environmental preferences by*

purchasing ecolabeled products". Henninger (2015) finds that consumers might be influenced by an ecolabel but still purchase fashion items that lack ecolabels.

This cognitive dissonance – where stated beliefs about sustainability do not always translate into purchase behaviour – can be explained by using Entwistle's framework (2015) '*situated bodily practice*'. This approach views consumer choices as shaped by a complex network of factors, including fashion trends, social mobility, economic constraints, social norms, and personal values. Day-to-day purchasing decisions in fashion thus reflect a multifaceted interaction between cultural influences, individual priorities, and bodily aesthetics and not as decisions made solely on one isolated factor.

While some studies (Brad et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2017) suggest there is a willingness to pay more for sustainable products, it is important to interpret these findings carefully, as they are not always specific to textile fashion. Unlike food, where sustainable choices often have direct personal health benefits, the motivation to choose eco-friendly fashion products is less immediate and more abstract (Lou and Xu, 2024). It is here important to note the challenges of conducting research in an under-researched area, as this often requires turning to grey literature produced by professional firms. In this case, the consultancy report referenced did not specifically focus on textile fashion consumers and is no longer available online, highlighting the limitations and accessibility issues of relying on such sources for academic research.

Furthermore, Lou and Xu (2024) highlight that in certain markets, such as the US denim sector, consumers prioritise price and brand over ecolabels and Henninger (2015, p. 6022) finds that "*whilst consumers are interested in purchasing garments that have an ecolabel on them, they are neither always aware of them nor willing to pay a price premium.*". This preference illustrates the challenge of conveying the value of sustainability in fashion, especially when the ethical benefits of a garment are not outwardly visible. As a result, while an ecolabel might signify a commitment to sustainable practices, it may hold little influence unless consumers recognise and trust the label.

These insights underscore the limitations of ecolabels as stand-alone motivators for sustainable fashion choices they also offer valuable insights that are useful for developing effective label certifications. The challenge lies in not only improving ecolabel visibility and consumer awareness but also in fostering a broader understanding of what these certifications signify. To effectively influence purchasing decisions, ecolabels must be part of a systems approach that includes consumer education and accessible information on the environmental and social impact of fashion products (Henninger, 2015; Lou and Xu, 2024).

2.2. Conceptual Framework

This study builds on theoretical insights from information asymmetry and consumer and producer uncertainty in the context of ecolabels (Cashore, 2002; Darnall et al., 2018; Darnall and Carmin, 2005). Ecolabels, as information-based instruments, are designed to reduce the information gap between producers and consumers about a product's environmental impact. However, the proliferation of ecolabels, the lack of standardisation, and the complexity of assessment methods create significant search costs for consumers and uncertainty, leading to suboptimal purchasing decisions. Additionally,

the large number of ecolabels increase producer uncertainty as well as their cost due to the adoption of multiple ecolabels (Darnall et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of four overarching key-dimensions and two sub-dimensions, see Table 1 for details.

Source: Authors

Our conceptual framework seen in Figure 1, details in Table 1, proposes four key dimensions with two sub-dimensions to reduce information asymmetry and uncertainty and enhance ecolabel effectiveness:

- **Standardisation of Environmental Attributes:** Ecolabels in the Textile and Fashion Industry (TFI) vary widely in terms of the environmental attributes they assess, such as carbon footprint, water usage, and biodiversity. This lack of uniformity complicates direct comparisons between ecolabels, adding to consumer confusion (Boström and Micheletti, 2016). Our framework suggests that standardising the assessment of key environmental attributes or, at a minimum, providing clear, comparable information across labels, could greatly improve consumer decision-making. In this report we focus on climate change while also considering the five additional planetary priorities (see Box 2) critical for mitigating global environmental pressures
- **Improved Transparency in Monitoring and Certification Processes:** Ecolabels differ in terms of the credibility of their certification processes, which can be self-assessed, sponsor-verified, or third-party verified (Darnall et al., 2018). Our framework emphasises the importance of third-party verification as a means of enhancing the credibility of ecolabels and reducing ambiguity confusion among consumers. Third-party verification not only ensures the robustness of sustainability claims but also fosters trust among consumers. Transparency in the verification process is also crucial, allowing consumers to understand the relationship between the company and the certifying organisation.
 - **Sub-dimension:** Verificatory Ownership. Examining the verificatory business setup helps to understand the ownership and governance structure of the verification body.

The structures of the certifying entities influence the independence and credibility of the certification process (Darnall et al., 2018; Henninger, 2015).

- **Lifecycle and Value Chain Consideration:** Given the globalised nature of the TFI, where most environmental impacts occur outside the country of consumption, ecolabels should cover the entire lifecycle of a product. This includes cradle-to-grave assessments that account for the environmental footprint from raw material extraction to disposal. By promoting ecolabels that evaluate the complete lifecycle of products, firms can provide consumers with a more accurate reflection of the product's environmental impact, thus addressing the broader value chain's externalities (Niinimäki et al., 2020).
 - **Sub-dimension: Material Area.** Determining which specific parts of the garment are verified, highlighting the extent to which each component of the product is assessed in the ecolabelling process.
- **Effective Communication of Ecolabel Information.** Ecolabels target two different audiences, Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B). Understanding how the information about ecolabels is effectively conveyed to diverse stakeholders and audiences is crucial for the effectiveness of an ecolabel. Consumer sustainability concerns, awareness and perception of ecolabels is directly influencing ecolabels potential to influencing purchasing decisions (KPMG, 2023; Lou and Xu, 2024).

By addressing these dimensions, our conceptual framework aims to improve the transparency, comparability, and trustworthiness of ecolabels within the TFI, thereby enhancing their effectiveness in signalling environmental performance and guiding both consumer behaviour and firm strategies toward sustainability.

3. Methodology: An Iterative, Qualitative Assessment Approach

We used an exploratory, qualitative research approach that included review, mapping and analysis of ecolabels used in the case of the TFI. We find that a case study approach is a suitable method for investigating the phenomenon of ecolabels within the Textile and Fashion Industry (TFI). This method allows for an in-depth exploration of how ecolabels are used, perceived, and relate to sustainability practices within the TFI. Case study is described by Yin (2009, p. 2) as a potent method when

“[...] the richness of the phenomenon and the extensiveness of the real-life context require case study investigators to cope with a technically distinctive situation: There will be many more variables of interest than data points.”

Our methodology involves key steps carried out through an iterative process to systematically address the biases and limitations inherent in the online information on ecolabels. This method allows for continuous refinement and validation of data, ensuring a more accurate and comprehensive analysis. Figure 1 illustrates the iterative process by which we systematically studied the ecolabels used within the TFI.

We collected data from various sources to compile a comprehensive list of the abundance of ecolabels available on the market and used by the TFI (see section 3.1). All information regarding the ecolabels, their standards, and eco-credentials was gathered from publicly available ecolabel websites. This approach is a valid method for document analysis (Bowen, 2009) and serves as a primary source of information for consumers interested in ecolabel details.

Figure 2. Methodology for Assessing Ecolabels in the Textile and Fashion Industry (TFI). This figure illustrates the iterative process of systematically studying the ecolabels used within the TFI. Our methodology involves key steps carried out through an iterative process. Figure adapted from Yin (2009).

Source: Authors

However, using online documents as sources for research entails several limitations as they are generally created for purposes other than research. They often lack the detailed information necessary for comprehensive analysis required to thoroughly assess environmental aspects. The accessibility of some online documents can be challenging. In some cases, information is assumingly deliberately withheld from public access or placed behind paywalls, making it difficult to retrieve essential data. The available documents may reflect biased selectivity, particularly within organisational contexts. Information accessible to the public are often those that align with the organisation's policies and agendas, which tends to skew the representation of information (Yin, 2009).

3.1. Data Collection

To gain a thorough understanding of ecolabels we conducted searches for academic literature using Web of Science, a global coverage citation database scope frequently used in bibliometric studies, and spans across academic disciplines. Additionally, we reviewed grey literature on ecolabels including

consultancy reports relating to ecolabels in general and the fashion industry in particular (Brad et al., 2018; Dodd et al., 2013; ETC/CE, 2022; KPMG, 2023; McKinsey & Company, 2023), a selection of reports and EU documents relating to the Green Deal and the TFI (Arribas et al., 2024; European Commission, 2024; Legarduer and Ospital, 2024), and EU documents relating to the EU ecolabel (European Commission, 2019, 2014, 2009).

We began with the Ecolabel Index, a global directory of ecolabels, which has compiled a list of 104 ecolabels on textiles (Ecolabel Index, 2024) and is the most referenced source in the academic literature we found (Darnall et al., 2018; Ranasinghe and Jayasooriya, 2021; Ziyeh and Cinelli, 2023). This list was supplemented with information from the Fashion United, an international B2B platform for the global apparel fashion industry (Fashion United, 2024) and also with information from the app 'Ecolabel guide' presented by Global Ecolabelling Network (2019), a nonprofit organisation of ecolabels worldwide. In total 155 certifiers and ecolabels were identified from different sources, see Appendix B. We assume we have not missed any significant ecolabels. We ensured all URLs (Uniform Resource Locator) were available in English and ecolabels were active and relevant to textile apparel. We excluded labels without English-language websites.

Ecolabels vary in their geographic scope which can be national, regional, or global. National ecolabels are recognized and applied within a single country, making them relevant for textile and fashion products that are produced and/or consumed domestically. Regional ecolabels cover multiple countries within a particular region, such as the European Union or North America, and are suited for textile and fashion products traded within these regions. Global ecolabels, on the other hand, are recognized and applicable worldwide. These ecolabels are particularly relevant for textile and fashion products involved in international trade and consumed across different continents. For this study we only include on ecolabels available in the UK and exclude ecolabels designed for exclusive domestic use within various nations outside the UK. We assume these are not predominantly used by UK firms or for clothing sold in the UK.

We also excluded ecolabels that focus on textiles not used for clothing such as carpets, furniture textiles and indoor quality. Ecolabels that focus on the welfare of farmed animals are considered to use an ethical standard and excluded unless they do directly mention environmental impacts.

We find that the Ecolabel Index list needs updating. The Ecolabel Index list is claimed to include 104 entities, but upon closer examination, there are only 103 entities listed. After reviewing the list according to our criteria, 39 certifiers remained who collectively manage 51 ecolabels that meet the definition of ecolabels and are applicable to the fashion and textile industry.

Of the 24 additional 'ecolabels' on Fashion United's list, only eight meet the definition of ecolabelling and are used by the fashion and textile industry. Of those excluded, seven are certifiers or advocacy groups, one is not relevant for the fashion and textile industry. After this review, 44 ecolabels remained for further analysis, see Figure 3.

foundation for evaluating and comparing ecolabels in a way that enhances transparency and facilitates meaningful comparisons.

Table 1. Summary of the codes used for mapping ecolabel according to our conceptual framework

CATEGORY	CATEGORY CODES
Standardisation of Environmental Attributes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change • Biodiversity loss • Freshwater change • Land system change • Chemical pollution and other novel entities • Altered Nitrogen & Phosphorus flows
Improved Transparency in Monitoring and Certification Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 14024, Type I • 3rd party verified • 2nd party verified • Self-declared
<i>Sub-dimension</i> Verificatory Ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private • Public • Non-profit
Lifecycle and Value Chain Consideration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cradle-to-Grave • Cradle-to-Gate • Gate-to-Gate • Gate-to-Grave • Cradle-to-Cradle
<i>Sub-dimension</i> Material area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final Product (Garment) • Component (Fiber) • Process (Firm/Organisational level)
Effective Communication of Ecolabel Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business-to-consumer (B2C) • Business-to-business (B2B)

Source: Authors

Standardisation of Environmental Attributes

By considering environmental attributes – focusing on climate change and five additional critical planetary priorities, see Cornell et al. (2021) – our framework addresses the most pressing global environmental issues. The categories we use align with those commonly applied in textile Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs), as noted by Sandin and colleagues (2019), see Box 3 for information about what LCA is. Importantly, the planetary boundaries framework, see Box 2, emphasizes the need for actions to mitigate climate change through a systems approach that considers the interconnections among environmental areas.

We map alternatives to conventional cotton, such as organic cotton, Cotton Made in Africa, and Better Cotton, in alignment with the findings made by Cornell and her team (2021). They state that although organic cotton has a lower carbon footprint compared to cotton produced with agrochemicals, its potential to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions is limited. We also consider that the share of organic cotton is likely to be lower than 0.4% of total fibre use for textile fashion (Niinimäki et al., 2020; Textile Exchange, 2022). Following this, in this analysis we do not code organic cotton as

targeting climate change. However, we have included metrics for biodiversity loss, freshwater use, chemical pollution, nitrogen and phosphorus use, and land use changes, as these aspects can be positively influenced by alternative cotton practices, depending on the specific standards and methods employed.

Box 2. Planetary priorities for sustainable firms

The planetary boundaries¹ framework demonstrates how human activities have shifted Earth's natural processes away from the stable conditions of the Holocene epoch, a period of about 10,000 years that allowed human societies to establish and thrive due to its relative climate and ecological stability. The further the world goes beyond this 'safe operating space', the higher the risks of disruptive environmental change. The framework assesses nine critical processes currently under acute pressure, exacerbated by ongoing production and consumption trends, leading to unprecedented system-shifting patterns of human-driven environmental change. This underscores the importance of science-informed priorities for global responsibility in resource use and mitigating environmental harms to avoid a much more uncertain future.

The policy-relevant framework provides a systemic basis for responding to the changing dynamics of the whole Earth, rather than treating environmental changes as separate reasons for concern. Some processes in the framework are already acutely under pressure, and current production and consumption trends are making the problems worse. A focus on these processes defines scientific priorities for global responsibility on resource use and environmental harms.

The planetary priorities for sustainable firms are the processes that are already far outside the 'safe operating space' and where global trends are worsening² despite international environmental agreements.

The six priority actions are not isolated challenges; rather, they involve tightly interconnected Earth system processes linked to human-driven changes in the Earth system. As human-caused pressure on one boundary continues to intensify, the 'operating space' demarcated by the others will shrink – but in poorly predictable ways. These six priorities are focal points that firms already address and have tools and methods such as product life-cycle impact analyses, foot-printing, and materiality assessments that help assess their work.

Figure from Cornell and Palm (2024).

¹ Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., et al. (2009). Planetary Boundaries: Exploring the Safe Operating Space for Humanity. *Ecology and Society*, 14(2), Art. 32. <http://www.ecologyandsociety.org/vol14/iss2/art32>.

² Cornell, Sarah, Tiina Häyhä, and Celinda Palm. "A Sustainable and Resilient Circular Fashion and Textiles Industry" Stockholm University's Stockholm Resilience Centre for the Ellen MacArthur Foundation and H&M Group, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4561847>; Cornell, Sarah E., and Celinda Palm. "How Can a Rubik's Cube Help You Understand the Global Environmental Sustainability Challenge?," 2024. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12592469>.

Box 3. Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA)

The UN Environment Programme (1996) explains that the aim of Lifecycle Assessment (LCA) is to promote more sustainable production and consumption practices through a scientific and objective approach. LCA considers the overall environmental consequences of a product and evaluates the environmental impacts throughout its entire life cycle using key characteristics (UNEP, 1996):

- **Comprehensive Analysis.** LCA analyses every stage of a product's life cycle, including extraction, processing, manufacturing, transportation, use, maintenance, recycling, and disposal.
- **Decision Support Tool.** It provides objective, data-driven insights into the environmental effects of products, aiding decision-making for governments, companies, NGOs, and consumers.
- **Complex Process.** LCA is a “cradle to grave” analysis that examines the use of resources and the release of hazardous substances, addressing both global issues like climate change and local concerns such as toxic emissions.
- **Stages of Assessment.** The assessment occurs in three stages: identifying and quantifying environmental loads (energy and materials used, emissions, and waste), evaluating potential impacts of these loads, and identifying opportunities for environmental improvements.

Sandin and colleagues (2019) present a thorough investigation to the environmental impact of textile fibers. The key categories of LCA they use to assess environmental impacts correspond to the ones we use, see Table 1 and Box 2:

- **Climate change.** Assesses greenhouse gas emissions primarily expressed in terms of Global Warming Potential (GWP).
- **Biodiversity loss.** Typically integrated within broader environmental impact categories, such as land use change and ecotoxicity.
- **Water use/depletion.** Assesses both the volume and sources of water consumed especially in fibre cultivation and textile dyeing processes.
- **Toxicity.** Indicators assess the potential harmful effects of substances used in the textile production process on human health, ecosystems, and the environment. This includes substances such as dyes, chemicals, pesticides, and heavy metals.
- **Eutrophication Potential.** Assesses the nutrient runoff (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus) from fertilisers used in fibre cultivation, leading to nutrient enrichment in water bodies.
- **Land use change.** Assesses the environmental impacts associated with changes in land use, such as the conversion of forests or wetlands into agricultural land for fibre production.

Improved Transparency in Monitoring and Certification Processes

There are different ways through which a product can be accredited an ecolabel. The different processes used reflect impartiality of claims, see Figure 4. We also examine the verificatory ownership, which influences credibility and public trust (Darnall et al., 2018), see Table 2.

Figure 4. Three main types of verification processes: 1st, 2nd, and 3rd party verified.
 Source: Authors

We code for first- to third-party verification levels, and for ISO Type I ecolabels which are designed for and used by various industries including TFI. “ISO 14024 Environmental labels and declarations ecolabels”, e.g. Type I, are third-party verified, assessment, based on multiple criteria rather than a single environmental attribute, and environmental impacts are considered throughout the lifecycle. For more information about ISO, see Box 4. We also assess the verificatory business setup and structure our coding according to private, nonprofit or public to understand the ownership and governance structure of the verification body.

Table 2. Classification of eco-credential standards. The classification Type I, Type II, and Type III is formalised by the ISO 14020 series standards.

Full name	Verification	Description provided by ISO (iso.org)
ISO 14024 , Environmental labels and declarations Type I environmental labelling – Principles and procedures	Third-party verified ecolabels based on multiple criteria and life cycle considerations.	<i>“voluntary, multiple-criteria-based third party (3.7) programme that awards a licence (3.13) which authorizes the use of environmental labels on products (3.2) indicating overall environmental preferability of a product within a particular product category (3.3) based on life cycle considerations”</i>
Three types of verification for ecolabels that do not formalise with the ISO 14024 standard		
Second-party verified Assessments by firms with a direct interest in the product/process, such as industry associations or buyers, lack the impartiality that third-party verifications offer.	Third-party verified The environmental assessments are based on third-party verification.	Self-declared (First-party claimed) environmental claims without third- or second-party verifications.

Source: Authors

Box 4. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO)

ISO is a non-governmental international organisation. Its primary aim is to promote global proprietary, industrial, and commercial standards of products and services. ISO standards are created through a consensus process of experts that draft and review the standards to meet the needs and expectations of global markets. The organization comprises national standards bodies from over 160 countries, with each member representing ISO in its respective country and contributing to the development and maintenance of standards. Users must pay to acquire ISO standards, access guidelines, and find information about the standards development process.

More information found on www.iso.org

While ISO standards offer significant advantages in promoting global consistency, consumer trust, and international trade facilitation, their paywall-protected structure and high compliance costs limit accessibility and may disproportionately benefit larger organisations, potentially hinder the diversity of ecolabels within the textile fashion industry (TFI). Considering that EU policy advocates for ISO Type I labels (European Commission, 2022a), increasing access to these standards could significantly enhance the inclusiveness of SMEs and increases the use ecolabels that meet high environmental standards within the textile fashion industry.

Lifecycle and Value Chain Considerations

To understand what part of the final product is considered in the ecolabel, we map the value chain stages of the lifecycle, Figure 5. We also identify the material area of certification by coding for component (fibre), final product or process.

Figure 5. Various scopes of the value chain in product life cycle assessments. The figure illustrates the different value chain scopes covered by various ecolabels within the Textile and Fashion Industry. Each scope represents distinct stages of the value chain, such as cradle-to-gate, gate-to-gate, cradle-to-grave, and cradle-to-cradle highlighting the varying degrees to which ecolabels address the environmental impact throughout the lifecycle of a product.
Source: Authors

- **Cradle-to-Cradle:** A business strategy that aims to mimic the regenerative cycle of nature in which waste is reused. Products are created in a way that at the end of their life cycle, they can be completely recycled or biodegraded, creating a closed-loop system.
- **Cradle-to-Grave:** Refers to the entire life cycle of a product, from the extraction of raw materials (cradle) to the end of the product's life (grave). This scope includes all stages such as raw material extraction, manufacturing, distribution, use, and disposal or recycling.
- **Cradle-to-Gate:** Covers the life cycle stages from the extraction of raw materials (cradle) up to the point where the product leaves the cut & sew (gate). This scope includes raw material extraction, transportation, and manufacturing processes.
- **Gate-to-Grave:** Covers the life cycle stages from when the product leaves the cut & sew (gate) to its disposal or end-of-life (grave). This scope includes distribution, use, and disposal phases.
- **Gate-to-Gate:** Refers to the environmental impact of processes that occur between two specific points within the production phase. This scope focuses typically on the impacts from one process to another within the manufacturing stage.

Effective Communication of Ecolabel Information

To assess the intended audience, we code for Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B).

4. Findings, Analysis, and Discussion of Key Dimensions of Ecolabels

In total, we identified 44 ecolabels that meet the criteria we specified in the methodology: they have websites with standards available in English, are applicable international and/or U.K markets, and are used by the TFI. Table 3 shows an overview of the identified ecolabels used within the TFI. These ecolabels were assessed and coded based on our conceptual framework. In Figure 7-14 we present the findings either as number of ecolabels or as percentages relative to the total ecolabels identified. The discussion of these findings is structured according to our conceptual framework.

Table 3. Overview of 44 International and UK Ecolabels Used in the TFI

Overall: Green = Yes, Red = No, Grey = n.a

Under: Communication channel, B2C = Business-to-Consumer, B2B = Business-to-Business; Verifier ownership, N-P = non-profit, P = private, Publ. = public; Geographical scope, Int = International, Reg. EU = European Union, Nat. UK = United Kingdom; ISO Type “I” = ISO 14024 Type I; Source, EI = Ecolabel Index, FU = Fashion United, EGA = Ecolabel Guide App.

Ecolabel	Communication channels	Material area	Requirements to reduce GHG emissions		Social & Environmental	Only mass recycled materials	Organic agriculture of fibres	Environmental attributes					Verifier Ownership	Geographical scope	Value chain scope	ISO Type	1-2-3 party verification	Launch year	Source	Certifier website
			Climate change	Biodiversity				Freshwater change	Chemical pollution and substances	Altered P&N flows	Land system change									
ABNT Ecolabel	B2C	Component										N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2007	EI	abnt.org.br	
B Corporation	B2B	Process incl. component										N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2006	EI	bcorporation.net	
Better Cotton Initiative	B2C	Component										N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2009	EI	bettercotton.org	
Blue Angel	B2C	Final product										N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	I	3rd	1978	EI	blauer-engel.de	
bluesign® standard	B2C	Final product										Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2000	EI	bluesign.com	
Carbon Neutral Certification	B2B	Process										Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2002	EI	carbonneutral.com	
Carbon Reduction Label	B2C	Final product										Publ.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2001	EI	carbontrust.com	
CarbonFree® Certified	B2C	Process										Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2009	EI	shop.climeco.com	
Certified Wildlife Friendly®	B2C	Final product										N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2007	EI	wildlifefriendly.org	
Compostability Mark of European Bioplastics	B2C	Final product										N-P	Reg.EU	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	1993	EI	european-bioplastics.org	
Cotton Made in Africa	B2C	Component										N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2005	EI	cottonmadeinafrica.org	
Cradle to Cradle Certified (CM) Products Program	B2C	Final product										N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-cradle	n.a	3rd	2005	EI	c2ccertified.org	
EU Ecolabel	B2C	Final product										Publ.	Reg.EU	Cradle-to-grave	I	3rd	1992	EI	environment.ec.europa.eu	

Fairtrade	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	1994	EI	fairtrade.net
Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS)	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2006	EI	globalstandard.org
Green Shape	B2C	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	1st	2010	EI	csrreport.vaude.com
Green Tick - Sustainable	B2C	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	1998	EI	greentick.com
GreenCircle - Carbon Footprint reduction	B2B	Process									Priv.	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2017	EI	greencirclecertified.com
GreenCircle - Dematerialization	B2B	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2014	EI	greencirclecertified.com
GreenCircle - Life Cycle Assessment Optimized	B2C	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2018	EI	greencirclecertified.com
GreenCircle - Product Optimization	B2C	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2013	EI	greencirclecertified.com
GreenCircle - Recycled content, Recycled material, Closed Loop Product	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2009	EI	www.greencirclecertified.com
GreenCircle - Sustainable Energy Practices	B2B	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2017	EI	greencirclecertified.com
LowCO2 Certification	B2B	Process									N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2005	EI	noco2.com.au
Made Safe	B2C	Component									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2015	FU	madesafe.org
Naturland e.V.	B2C	Component									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	1982	EI	naturland.de
NoCO2 Certification	B2C	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2006	EI	noco2.com.au
Nordic Ecolabel or "Swan"	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	l	3rd	1989	EI	nordic-swan-ecolabel.org
Oeko-Tex Standard 101 - Made in Green	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2014	EI	oeko-tex.com
Oeko-Tex Standard 102 - Standard 100	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	1992	EI	oeko-tex.com
Oeko-Tex Standard 103 - Organic Cotton	B2C	Component									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2021	EI	www.oekotex.com
Oeko-Tex Standard 104 - STeP	B2B	Process									N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2013	EI	oeko-tex.com
Oeko-Tex Standard 105 - Eco Passport	B2B	Component									N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2005	EI	oeko-tex.com
Organic content Standard	B2B	Component									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2013	EI	textileexchange.org
Organic Farmers & Growers Certification	B2C	Component									N-P	Nat.UK	Gate-to-grave	n.a	3rd	1973	EI	ofgorganic.org

Rainforest Alliance	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	1987	ECA	rainforest-alliance.org
Recycled Claim Standard	B2C	Final product									Priv.	Int.	Gate-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2011	EI	scsglobalservices.com
Regenerative Organic Certified	B2C	Component									N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2020	FU	regenorganic.org
Responsible Wool Standard	B2C	Component									Priv.	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2016	EI	scsglobalservices.com
Sane Standard	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2019	FU	sanestandard.com
SMaRT Consensus Sustainable Product Standards	B2C	Final product									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-grave	n.a	3rd	2015	EI	mts.sustainableproducts.com
Soil Association Organic Standard	B2C	Component									N-P	Nat.UK	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	1946	EI	soilassociation.org
World Fair Trade Organization (WFTO)	B2B	Process									N-P	Int.	Cradle-to-gate	n.a	3rd	1958	FU	wfto.com
ZQ Natural Fibre	B2C	Component									N-P	Int.	Gate-to-gate	n.a	3rd	2006	EI	discoverzq.com

Source: Authors

4.1. Inconsistency of Environmental Attributes

There is inconsistency in the environmental attributes included in different standards (see Figure 6). Nearly half of the ecolabels do not address climate change in their standards, with this omission largely due to the prevalence of ecolabels certifying organic cotton. Notably, nine out of ten organic cotton ecolabels do not include climate change as a criterion, though they account for other environmental attributes (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Distribution of ecolabels addressing climate change. Distribution of ecolabels addressing climate change exclusively or in combination with specific environmental attributes, differentiated by business-to-consumer (B2C) and business-to-business (B2B) audiences.

Source: Authors

Ecolabels focusing solely on "climate change" tend to target a B2B audience, while those addressing both "climate change and biodiversity loss" are mainly directed towards a B2C audience (see Figure 8). The share of ecolabels including both climate change and biodiversity is low among those targeting both B2C and B2B audiences. Many B2C ecolabels prioritize chemicals, coded as "chemical pollution," likely due to consumer concerns about harmful chemicals in contact with skin, which are more immediate than distant global environmental impacts.

Assessing environmental attributes poses significant challenges. Detailed information on standards is often accessible only through lengthy, technical documentation not intended for consumers. There is a lack of uniformity and transparency regarding environmental attributes. Firms within the TFI seek scientific evidence to guide their strategic decisions. However, the lack of uniformity and transparent data obstructs the development of standardised assessment methods, making it challenging to compare findings across studies.

The differences in interest in climate change compared to other environmental attributes (see Figure 6 and Figure 7) indicate inconsistency due to cherry-picking and a lack of a scientific, systems approach, complicating comparisons between ecolabels for all stakeholders.

Figure 7. Percentage distribution of ecolabels across market types—34 Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and 10 Business-to-Business (B2B)—classified by environmental focus area within six defined environmental attributes (e.g. the six planetary priorities; see Box 2).

Source: Authors

Policymakers face the challenge of regulating a global TFI and guiding consumers toward making sustainable choices. It is rarely stated on websites which environmental attributes are considered. Standards often define verification processes and compliance requirements well, but lack clear links to specific environmental aspects, certification requirements, and reasons for rejecting potential clients. Even when ISO 14024 standards are used, environmental attributes vary, making comparisons across ecolabels and materials difficult.

TFI ecolabels are voluntary and while the EU has set ambitious goals to make the TFI climate-neutral (European Commission, 2022), the complexity of the TFI - its global and complex value chains and diverse fibre compositions – poses challenges to creating a universal policy with standardised criteria applicable to all garments. As a result, concerned consumers are likely to be confused when trying to determine what aspects of a product are verified and whether these align with their ethical values (Boström and Micheletti, 2016).

4.2. Improved Transparency in Monitoring and Certification Processes

Our analysis shows that 40 ecolabels are verified by a third party, three are ISO 14024 Type I (Blue Angel, EU Ecolabel, Nordic Ecolabel 'Swan'), and one is self-assessed (Vaude). The most common firm structure among these ecolabels is non-profit, see Figure 8.

Figure 8. Distribution of verificatory ownership for ecolabels by market type (B2B and B2C)

This figure displays the distribution of ecolabel verificatory ownership types – non-profit, private, and public – segmented by market type, with comparisons across Business-to-Business (B2B) and Business-to-Consumer (B2C) categories

Source: Authors

The use of third-party verifiers offers benefits for consumers and the TFI firms alike. Independent verification increases the likelihood that standard assessments are accurate and trustworthy. For TFI firms, it aligns with the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles, which mandates that voluntary sustainability labels covering environmental or social aspects must rely on third-party verification or established by public authorities. Furthermore, the EU Strategy clearly states that “*General environmental claims, such as “green”, “eco-friendly”, “good for the environment”, will be allowed only if underpinned by recognised excellence in environmental performance, notably based on the EU Ecolabel, type I ecolabels, or specific EU legislation relevant to the claim*” (European Commission, 2022. p. 6).

However, on third-party verifier websites criteria and standards is often presented in vague but appealing wordings such as ‘*good for the environment*’ (Federal Ministry for the Environment, 2024), ‘*promotes resource efficiency, reduced climate impact, a non-toxic circular economy and conservation of biodiversity*’ (Nordic Ecolabelling, 2024). These websites act as promotional tools, as shop windows, rather than educational resources, focusing on marketing the ecolabels rather than providing detailed information

Our review of verifier websites revealed that non-profit status is usually clearly stated, while private, for-profit verifiers are less transparent about their ownership, often appearing similar to non-profits. This aligns with observations by Darnall and colleagues (2018, p. 953), who noted that “*consumers appear to be more distrustful of ecolabels sponsored by business associations*”. The lack of transparency among for-profit verifiers may contribute to this distrust suggests that the lack of transparency among for-profit verifiers may contribute to a similar distrust.

To avoid a potential conflict of interest, robust ecolabel schemes should separate the role of the certifier – who is responsible for issuing the ecolabel – and the verifier – whose role it is to audit or assess the data. However, we find a lack of transparency; the roles are rarely explicitly stated on many ecolabel websites, creating ambiguity about who is responsible setting the standards and for verifying claims.

4.3. Lifecycle and Value Chain Consideration

Our findings in

Figure 9-11 illustrate that ecolabels are allocated across different stages and elements of the production cycle, highlighting variations in sustainability certification approaches based on material area and value chain stages. Cradle-to-grave is the value chain scope most used for ecolabels targeting a B2C audience alongside final products. The second most common value chain scope for B2C ecolabels are textile fibres – components – which are gate-to-gate verified. Ecolabels certifying firms processes are all for a B2B audience including one certifying process and component. Figure 12 and Figure 13 show that there is an increasing focus on cradle-to-grave ecolabels.

Figure 9. Total count of ecolabels distributed across market types, Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B), and categorised value chain scope: Cradle-to-Grave, Cradle-to-Gate, Gate-to-Gate, Gate-to-Grave, Cradle-to-cradle.

Source: Authors

However, the value chain perspective used by most ecolabels overlooks the crucial distinction between absolute and relative sustainability. Current ecolabel standards primarily focus on relative sustainability, which aims to improve existing production practices. As a result, the footprint of a garment may be marked as reduced, masking the fact that the total number of garments produced has increased, leading to higher overall environmental impact. These standards do not address absolute sustainability, which considers the total environmental impact of production at scale. Consequently, even if a product is labelled as sustainable, the sheer volume of its production can still result in significant environmental harm.

Figure 10. Total count of ecolabels distributed across market types, Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B), and categorised by material focus areas: Final Product, Component, Process, and Process & Component.

Source: Authors

Figure 11. Distribution of ecolabels across value chain scopes, market types, and material focus areas. The figure illustrates the allocation of ecolabels according to value chain scope classifications—cradle-to-gate, cradle-to-grave, gate-to-gate, and gate-to-grave—alongside market type distinctions: Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B). Material focus areas are shown, as ecolabel distributions for Final Product, Component, Process, and Process & Component categories, highlighting how ecolabels address sustainability differently depending on market type and stages of the value chain.

Source: Authors

Furthermore, the narrow focus on specific value chain stages often ignores substantial environmental impacts earlier in the lifecycle, leaving gaps in sustainability assessments. For example, benefits at the resource extraction stage may be offset by high impacts during garment production, a fact not disclosed to consumers. Without considering all production phases, decisions based on incomplete data can lead to suboptimal sustainability outcomes.

The rise of cradle-to-grave ecolabels, largely driven by the growing interest in the circular economy, presents its own challenges. There is a lack of standardized data for assessing cradle-to-gate stages, and there is limited research on the circular economy to support potential benefits of various circular strategies (Cornell et al., 2021; Corvellec et al., 2022; Kirchherr et al., 2018). While cradle-to-grave certifications are most relevant to consumers, who typically purchase final products, these ecolabels often fail to disclose missing data, creating significant gaps in sustainability assessments.

Figure 12. Cumulative number of ecolabels launched over time, categorised by value chain scope and market type (Business-to-Consumer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B), and organised by targeted environmental focus areas. The timeline illustrates growth trends across various ecolabels, highlighting their focus within specific value chain stages and the intended market audience, thereby reflecting shifts in environmental certification priorities over time. ‘n.a’ refers to not applicable, for details see Appendix 1.

Source: Authors

4.4. Effective Communication of Ecolabel Information.

Our findings indicate that out of 44 ecolabels, 34 target a B2C audience, while 10 are aimed primarily at B2B stakeholders, see Figure 13. Of the 10 B2B-focused ecolabels, eight certify firms processes or specific components (such as fibres), while the remaining two certify final products. B2B ecolabels typically focus on climate change and firms’ processes. In contrast, B2C ecolabels are usually verified by non-profit entities, focus on climate change and chemicals, with final products being verified throughout the value chain e.g. cradle-to-grave.

Ecolabels are typically designed to influence consumer choices by distinguishing products in the marketplace and promoting sustainable production practices, so the differentiation between B2C and B2B ecolabels is logical. However, the way ecolabel information is communicated varies between these two audiences.

Previous studies have shown that ecolabels within the TFI are part of a broader business ecosystem, which includes not just firms but also policymakers, a context not captured by a simple value chain perspective (Palm, 2023b). Ecolabels used within TFI do not operate in isolation; as all environmental certifications (Iatridis and Kesidou, 2018), they evolve in response to shifts in regulatory, market, and consumer expectations, which is why tracking their development over time is valuable for all stakeholders (Figure 13).

One contributing factor to the increase of ecolabels certifying cradle-to-grave scope is the growing interest in circularity within the TFI and by policy initiatives (European Commission, 2022; UKRI, 2023; United Nations System Staff College UNSSC, 2020). Furthermore, increasingly consumers are becoming more aware, demanding resource sustainability and waste reduction. Following this, ecolabels targeting B2C audience are increasingly introduced that account for the entire lifecycle of products, ensuring that materials are reused, recycled, or safely decomposed at the end of their use.

Figure 13. Three timelines of the introduction of ecolabels for various audiences. Top section displays the cumulative number of ecolabels launched over time, providing an overview of the growth in ecolabel certifications. Middle section highlights the timeline of ecolabels intended for B2C markets, showcasing when these consumer-oriented ecolabels were introduced. Bottom section outlines the timeline of ecolabels designed for B2B markets, indicating launch dates of ecolabels for a business audience. Note: timeline shows currently active ecolabels only.

Source: Authors

However, the rise in ecolabels certifying cradle-to-grave value chain scope, see Figure 12, is masking crucial problems. There is a lack of standardized data for assessing cradle-to-gate stages, and limited research on the circular economy obscures the potential benefits of various circular strategies (Cornell et al., 2021; Corvellec et al., 2022; Kirchherr et al., 2018). While a cradle-to-grave scope is highly relevant for consumers, as they purchase final products, ecolabels are not fully transparent; they often fail to disclose missing data, creating large data gaps in these assessments.

It is noteworthy that while the TFI increasingly launches ecolabels with a cradle-to-grave value chain scope, claiming to control the entire value chain, they simultaneously state that more data is needed to accurately assess carbon emissions from their upstream and downstream activities., e.g. Scope 3 “*emissions [that] are a consequence of the activities of the company, but occur from sources not owned or controlled by the company*” (World Resources Institute, 2015, p. 25). This inconsistency creates a misleading impression that a product’s full environmental impact is being managed, when in reality, significant data gaps remain.

5. Key Strengths and Weaknesses of Ecolabels

Our findings address both the **strengths** e.g. standardization, enhanced transparency and lifecycle integration, and **weaknesses** e.g. lack consistency, fragmented sustainability approaches, and communication issues, of ecolabels in the TFI. Addressing these strengths and weaknesses is important as it will help firms, policymakers, customers to make informed decisions. In Table 4 we present opportunities and challenges of ecolabels in the industry based on our findings.

Table 4. Strengths and Weaknesses of Ecolabels in the TFI based on four key dimensions.

	Standardisation of environmental attributes	Improved transparency in monitoring and certification processes	Lifecycle and value chain consideration	Effective communication of ecolabel information
STRENGTHS	<p>Ecolabels as Catalysts for Alignment</p> <p>Ecolabels play an essential role in setting benchmarks for environmental attributes, including carbon emissions, water consumption, and biodiversity preservation. They help stakeholders to align key environmental priorities. Ecolabels with broad of environmental attributes reduce information asymmetries in both B2C and B2B markets. Ecolabels that manage to balance industry operations and consumer attitudes and expectations have potential to create market-wide sustainability trends.</p>	<p>Enhanced Transparency and Certification Credibility</p> <p>Through rigorous certification processes, particularly those involving third-party verification, ecolabels contribute significantly to transparency and trust in sustainability standards. Most ecolabels use third-party certification, underscoring a commitment to credible environmental assessments. The majority of ecolabel certifiers have a nonprofit ownership aligning with consumer preferences for independently vetted certifications, which enhances the perceived reliability of ecolabels.</p>	<p>Capability to adjust Lifecycle and Value Chain Integration</p> <p>Ecolabels in the TFI cover various lifecycle stages of its international complex, global value chain. The number of ecolabels claiming to assess the entire value chain, from cradle to grave, is increasing as the TFI demonstrates a strong and rapid response to policy mandates and consumer concerns, showing that TFI credit itself to have the capacity to adapt and position itself in evaluating the full value chain. This indicates ecolabels could increasingly contribute to a more transparent and environmentally responsible industry practices, and guide consumers toward more informed purchasing decisions.</p>	<p>Targeted Communication for Audience Differentiation</p> <p>Ecolabels function as an effective tool for disseminating sustainability information to B2C and B2B audiences. The bifurcation of the ecolabels provides opportunities to address the unique informational needs of each audience and helps reduce information asymmetries between producers, consumers, and firms. B2C labels can provide eco-credentials for consumers as a guide for making less un-sustainable purchase decisions. B2B labels support stakeholders through verification of processes and component-level attributes aiding sustainable value chain management.</p>
WEAKNESSES	<p>Limited Scientific Integration and Lack of a Systems Approach</p> <p>There is a problematic inconsistency and “cherry-picking” of environmental attributes used across different ecolabels, which hinder the development of standardized assessment methods, making comparisons difficult for firms and consumers. This undermines the ability of ecolabels to provide a comprehensive and accurate picture of a product’s sustainability, by failing to adopt a systems-based approach that considers the interconnectedness of environmental impacts throughout the product lifecycle. The assessment of environmental attributes is further complicated by the lack of accessible, uniform, and transparent information, which if available, is buried in lengthy technical documentation.</p>	<p>Lack of Clarity, Transparency, and Consumer Trust</p> <p>Vague and promotional language used on third-party verifier websites, point to a lack of clarity and transparency undermining the educational value of ecolabels, leaving consumers unable to make informed decisions based on true environmental impact of products. Lack of transparency regarding ownership and certifier vs verifier roles, further complicates trustworthiness and contributes to consumer distrust and scepticism regarding who is responsible for setting the standards and verifying claims. While EU policy endorse Type I ecolabels to underpin green marketing claims, few ecolabels within TFI are Type I. TFI is also challenged to comply to policy demands, while using marketing that responds to consumer attitudes and expectations.</p>	<p>Transparency Gaps, Consumer Distrust and Narrow Material Focus</p> <p>There is a lack of comprehensive and standardised data across the entire production cycle. Narrow scopes exclude critical environmental impacts from certain lifecycle stages, while broader scopes fail to disclose missing data, leading to gaps in sustainability assessments. A focus on relative sustainability, misleads consumers into thinking a product is truly sustainable. The disproportionate focus on organic cotton, which represents a small fraction of global textile production, overlooks synthetic fibres, limiting the effectiveness of providing a complete picture of environmental impact. Skewed focus, lack of transparency and data comprehensiveness obstructs informed, scientific decision-making, hinder overall effectiveness of TFI ecolabels.</p>	<p>Challenges in Consumer Comprehension and Communication</p> <p>There is inconsistency and complexity in how sustainability information is communicated to different audiences. Ecolabels suffer from either oversimplified messaging or overly technical language, both of which hinder their accessibility. Moreover, communication varies between B2C ecolabels focus on final products and broader environmental criteria while B2B ecolabels target specific processes or components. This mismatch, and unclear or incomplete data is confusing hindering informed, scientifically informed decisions. Business communication also has to make ecolabels compelling and attractive without the slipperiness of overstated claims, while complying with EU regulations requiring external communications to be supported by scientific evidence.</p>

Source: Authors

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

Ecolabels play a critical role in shaping sustainability practices within the textile and fashion industry (TFI) by setting benchmarks for environmental attributes, promoting transparency, and fostering lifecycle and value chain consideration. However, several challenges persist. While ecolabels help align environmental priorities and guide consumer purchasing decisions, their lack of scientific integration, inconsistent environmental attribute selection, and vague criteria hinder effective cross-label comparisons and limit consumer comprehension. Additionally, transparency gaps in certification processes, particularly regarding certifier ownership structures, contribute to consumer distrust.

Ecolabel criteria need to be continuously updated and evolved to remain relevant in response to new scientific findings, technological advancements, and evolving industry standards. However, there is currently no consensus within academia on how to define ecolabels, adding to the complexity and confusion among stakeholders regarding what constitutes an ecolabel. Hopefully, our definition below can serve as a starting point for discussions toward a consensus on the concept itself:

Ecolabels are voluntary self-regulation tools that indicate products (or processes) as environmentally preferable based on life-cycle considerations. Ecolabels signify that a product meet stated environmental and social criteria, claiming to have less negative environmental (and/or social) impacts compared to similar products. Ecolabels, with independently verified, credible, non-misleading information about the environmental impacts of products, differentiate products in the marketplace, aiming to promote more sustainable production and consumption practices.

Academic studies regarding ecolabels often selectively focus on individual aspects, contributing to inconsistencies and limiting comparability, despite the scientific foundation for global sustainability is clear and highlights the interconnectedness of global biophysical processes (Rockström et al., 2009: Box 2). It is only when academia and stakeholders adopt a systems and scientific approach, standardize criteria, and enhance communication strategies that ecolabels can be developed to better serve as credible, accessible tools for promoting sustainable practices and guiding both consumers and firms toward more environmentally responsible choices within the textile and fashion industry.

6.1. Recommendations for better ecolabels and strategies for implementation

To strengthen the effectiveness of ecolabels and facilitate a more sustainable, transparent industry, it is crucial that ecolabels address the existing weaknesses and build greater trust among stakeholders. The following four recommendations are proposed to achieve these goals:

- 1. Ensure consistency in environmental standards.**

Inconsistencies in environmental standards and criteria across different ecolabels pose a significant challenge, making it difficult for consumers to compare garment accurately. Ecolabels need standardised criteria and align with international sustainability frameworks, such as those set out by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This will allow for more reliable cross-label comparisons, improve the credibility and prevent the proliferation of misleading or vague claims.

2. **Adopt a more systems-based approach.**

One of the key weaknesses of current ecolabels is the lack of a comprehensive, systems-based approach to sustainability. Rather than focusing on isolated environmental attributes like carbon emissions or water consumption, ecolabels should take a systems approach that considers the interconnections between various environmental impacts throughout the lifecycle. By using a lifecycle approach that incorporates multiple environmental dimensions, ecolabels can more accurately reflect the true sustainability of textile fashion, reducing the risk of "cherry-picking" criteria and promoting a more complete and balanced view of sustainability. Importantly, adopting a system approach also applies to the value chain scopes. An inclusion of a narrow part of the value chain overlooks significant environmental impacts occurring earlier in the lifecycle, failing to capture the extent of the final products impacts that can result in suboptimal sustainability outcomes. Without considering all production phases throughout the entire value chain from at least cradle-to-gate, decisions based on incomplete data potentially lead to suboptimal sustainability outcomes.

3. **Strengthen ecolabel standards beyond third-party verification.**

While third-party verification of ecolabels in the TFI provides credibility and trust, it is not enough to ensure comprehensive sustainability practices. Current ecolabel standards focus on relative improvements rather than absolute sustainability, failing to account for the global environmental impact of large-scale production and missing the systemic understanding needed for meaningful environmental action. The varying standards, criteria, and reassessment schemes of ecolabels may contribute to vagueness, lack of transparency and even slipperiness in communications on what has been assessed and verified. This makes it difficult for consumers and stakeholders to determine which labels represent high sustainability standards. Consequently, a component or product certified by one ecolabel might not meet other ecolabels criteria, leading to gaps in sustainability practices. Additionally, the transparency issues in certification processes and criteria hinder consumers and stakeholders from verifying ecolabel claims, diminishing the value of third-party verification. Finally, even when using third-party verification, firms may still engage in greenwashing as they can meet the minimum certification requirements without making substantial changes to their practices. This undermines the whole purpose of ecolabels.

4. **Improve communication strategies.**

A major barrier to the effectiveness of ecolabels is the communication gap between certification bodies, firms, and consumers. Currently, ecolabels suffer from either oversimplified messaging or overly technical language, both of which hinder their accessibility. On one hand, some ecolabels reduce complex sustainability issues to simplistic claims that at best fail to convey the depth of the environmental impacts or criteria they cover, or present borderline greenwashing messages. On the other hand, some labels use dense, technical language that is difficult for the average consumer to interpret, creating confusion and reducing the label's effectiveness in guiding informed decisions. To address this, ecolabels need to strike a balance between accessibility and accuracy. Communication should be clear, simple, and consumer-friendly, while still conveying the necessary detail about the sustainability claims.

6.2. Limitations and areas for further research

Our analysis has a number of limitations, some of which could provide opportunities for future research. We did not examine the relationship between ecolabels and the environmental performance of firms in the TFI, nor did we include any negative social impacts.

More research is needed that takes a systems approach to understanding the negative social impacts of the TFI. A systems approach that acknowledges the interconnectedness of social and environmental factors can address many of the weaknesses, such as material efficiency, discussed in this report. Previous research indicates that focusing on isolated parts of the system and promoting piecemeal measures is insufficient to understand the complexity of the TFI or to provide the knowledge needed to reduce its negative impacts (Cornell et al., 2021; Palm, 2023a; Palm et al., 2021). Millward-Hopkins et al. (2018) also point to the irrelevance of categorizing metrics into separate domains and emphasizes the need for a socio-political narrative to guide assessments. Transdisciplinary systems research embracing co-creative dialogues between stakeholders and academics is more likely to co-generate new knowledge necessary for advancing sustainable fashion practices.

On this follows the need for research to understand whether, and how, ecolabels are linked to firms' overall sustainability strategies and targets. Ecolabels are just one component of a broader sustainability strategy, and a deeper understanding of their role in the business ecosystem is still lacking. A systems approach is essential to assess how firms' efforts can contribute meaningfully to global sustainability and to identify key areas where actions can have the greatest impact.

More research is also needed to investigate the frequency of use and adoption of the 44 ecolabels within the U.K. textile and fashion industry (TFI). This would help to better understand their market penetration and their effectiveness in guiding sustainable consumer and firms' practices. As noted by Arribas et al. (2024), although numerous environmental labels are used in the textile sector, there is currently no direct method to quantify their market penetration. As a result, it is difficult to assess the true success of these labels and identify the specific factors contributing to their effectiveness. Such insights could be valuable for revising the EU Ecolabel criteria for textile products.

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Appendices

Appendix A. 44 Ecolabels and their logos used in the TFI

Logos retrieved from certifiers websites.

	GreenCircle - Dematerialization		
	Naturland e.v.		
	Nordic Ecolabel or "Swan"		
	Oeko-Tex Standard 101 - Made in Green		
	Oeko-Tex Standard 102 - Standard 100		
	Oeko-Tex Standard 103 - Organic Cotton		
	Oeko-Tex Standard 104 - STeP		
	Oeko-Tex Standard 105 - Eco Passport		
	Organic Farmers & Growers Certification		
	Recycled Claim Standard		
	Responsible Wool Standard		
	SMaRT Consensus Sustainable Product Standards		
	Soil Association Organic Standard		
	ZQ Natural Fibre		
	bluesign® standard		
	Sane Standard		
	ABNT Ecolabel		
	B Corporation		
	Better Cotton Initiative		
	Blue Angel		
	Carbon Neutral Certification		
	GreenCircle - Product Optimization		
	GreenCircle - Sustainable Energy Practices		

Sources: Authors

Appendix B. Overview of all 155 certifiers and their ecolabels assessed in this study

Overall: Green = Yes, Red = No, Grey = n.a, X= not assessed, OE= Overarching Entity for multiple ecolabels

Name	Ecolabel	Active website	Certifies TFI Material areas	Social dimensions only	Comments	Source	Certifier website
ABNT Ecolabel	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies cotton in Brazil for a global market.	EI	abnt.org.br
Animal Welfare Approved	Y	Y	N	N	Certifies food.	EI	agreenerworld.org
B Corporation	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies process, ≈90 certified UK TF firms.	EI	bcorporation.net
BMP Certified Cotton	Y	Y	Y	N	A certification program focused on promoting sustainable, energy efficient, cotton production.	EI	mybmp.com.au
Better Cotton Initiative	Y	Y	Y	N	Sustainability organisation and ecolabel aimed at improving cotton farming practices globally.	EI	bettercotton.org
Blue Angel	Y	Y	Y	N	ISO Type I.	EI	blauer-engel.de
CRI Green Label	Y	Y	N	X	Ecolabel for carpets.	EI	carpet-rug.org
Carbon Neutral Certification	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel for offsetting Scope 1 and 2 carbon footprint.	EI	carbonneutral.com
Carbon Reduction Institute	X	Y	OE	N	Organisation, two ecolabels below listed separately	EI	noco2.com.au
<i>NoCO2 Certification</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel following a carbon emission audit.	EI	noco2.com.au
<i>LowCO2 Certification</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel following a carbon emission Scope 2 audit.	EI	noco2.com.au
Carbon Reduction Label	Y	Y	Y	N	Product carbon footprint ecolabel.	EI	carbontrust.com
CarbonCare	Y	Y	N	X	Carbon emission certification for the transport and logistics sector.	EI	carboncare.org
CarbonFree® Certified	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel no longer active.	EI	shop.climeco.com
Certified Humane Raised and Handled	Y	Y	Y	Y	Certifies that animals raised for dairy, lamb, poultry and beef products are treated in a humane manner.	EI	certifiedhumane.org
Certified Wildlife Friendly®	Y	Y	Y	N	Certification is concerned with the operational impacts on biodiversity.	EI	wildlifefriendly.org
China Environmental Labelling	Y	Y	Y	N	A Chinese national ecolabel.	EI	certrip.org
Climatop	X	N	X	X	No active website found.	EI	n.a
Compostability Mark of European Bioplastics - Seedling logo	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel for industrial compostability.	EI	european-bioplastics.org
Coop Naturaline: Switzerland	Y	Y	Y	N	A Swiss National ecolabel.	EI	coop.ch
Cradle to Cradle Certified(CM) Products Program	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel set to certify products are safe and healthy for humans and beneficial to the environment and society.	EI	c2ccertified.org
Danish Indoor Climate Label	Y	Y	N	X	Ecolabel for building materials, furniture and fixtures.	EI	indeklimateaerket.dk
Degree of Green®	Y	Y	N	X	Focus on 'healthy homes'.	EI	degreeofgreen.com

Demeter Biodynamic®	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies that Biodynamic farming practices have been used.	EI	demeter-usa.org
ECOLOGO	Y	Y	N	N	Standards för Building products.	EI	ul.com
EU Ecolabel	Y	Y	Y	N	ISO Type I.	EI	environment.ec.europa.eu
Earthsure	X	N	X	X	No active website found.	EI	n.a
Eco-Leaf	Y	Y	Y	N	A Japanese national ecolabel.	EI	ecoleaf-jemai.jp
EcoMark: Japan	X	Y	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	ecomark.jp
Ecocert	N	Y	X	N	Not an ecolabel but a thirdparty certification body for sustainable development.	EI	ecocert.com
Ecoproof	X	N	Y	N	No active website found.	EI	n.a
Ekologicky setrny vyrobek / Environmentally Friendly Product	X	Y	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	ekoznacka.cz
Environmental Choice New Zealand	X	N	X	X	No active website found.	EI	n.a
Environmental Product Declaration	N	N	X	X	Not an ecolabel but a standardized document that provides information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products.	EI	environdec.com
Etichetta ambientale	X	Y	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	assocai.it
Fair Labor Practices and Community Benefits	Y	Y	Y	Y	A social responsibility certification to complement Organic Fair Labor Practices and Community Benefits certification.	EI	scscertified.com
Fair Trade Certified	Y	Y	Y	N	A U.S national ecolabel.	EI	fairtradecertified.org
Fair for Life	Y	Y	Y	Y	Ecolabel for social accountability and fair trade in agricultural, manufacturing and trading operations.	EI	fairforlife.org
FairWertung	X	X	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	fairwertung.de
Fairtrade	Y	Y	Y	N	Fairtrade Textile Standard applies to operators employing hired workers in the textile supply chain processing Fairtrade certified cotton and/or other responsible fibres.	EI	fairtrade.net
Greenguard	Y	Y	N	N	Certifies interior products and materials.	EI	greenguard.org
GUT	Y	Y	N	N	Ceritfies textile floor covering.	EI	gut-ev.de
Global GreenTag Certified	Y	Y	N	N	Certifies interior textiles and materials.	EI	globalgreentag.com
Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS)	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies organic cotton, component and final product.	EI	global-standard.org
Textile Exchange	X	Y	OE	N	An organisation not an ecolabel. We include three of their certifications recycled, organic and wool fibers seperatly in this list.	EI	textileexchange.org
<i>Recycled Claim Standard and Global Recycled Standard</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Certified by Textile Exchange.	EI	textileexchange.org
<i>Organic content Standard</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Certified by Textile Exchange.	EI	textileexchange.org
Good Environmental Choice "Bra Miljöval"	Y	Y	N	N	No longer certifies textiles.	EI	bramiljoval.se
Good Environmental Choice Australia (GECA)	Y	Y	Y	N	An Australian national ecolabel.	EI	geca.eco
Good Shopping Guide Ethical Award	N	X	X	X	Not an ecolabel itself, but it awards ethical accreditations, including the Ethical Award.	EI	thegoodshoppingguide.com
GoodWeave	Y	Y	N	Y	Certifies carpets.	EI	goodweave.net
Green America's Green Business Certification	Y	Y	Y	N	An U.S national ecolabel. They provide and verifies the label "Green America's Certification Team will review your application and	EI	greenamerica.org

					respond within 10 days with any follow up questions or regarding the status of your application."		
Green Crane: Ukraine	Y	Y	Y	N	An Ukrainian national ecolabel.	EI	ecolabel.org.ua
Green Mark	X	X	X	X	No active website found.	EI	n.a
Green Products Standard	X	X	X	X	No active website found.	EI	n.a
Green Shape	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel for the 'Vaude' brand.	EI	csr-report.vaude.com
Green Tick - Sustainable	Y	Y	Y	N	The green Tick Organisation has nine different certifications. We only code for Sustainable since all the others fall under that standard.	EI	greentick.com
GreenCircle	X	Y	OE	X	Nine ecolabels listed seperatly below.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
<i>GreenCircle - Recycled content, Recycled material, Cloosed Loop Product</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies recycled material.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
<i>GreenCircle - Carbon Footprint reduction</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies carbon reduction.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
<i>GreenCircle</i>	Y	Y	N	N	A Certified Energy Savings Certification.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
<i>GreenCircle - Life Cycle Assessment Optimized</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies a commitment to continuous improvement.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
<i>GreenCircle - Product Optimization</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	A minimum of a 1% carbon emission reduction of a product is required to receive certification.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
<i>GreenCircle - Sustainable Energy Practices</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Certify claims that a product's energy usage in the manufacturing stage was reduced or the renewable/carbon-free energy usage has increased.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
<i>GreenCircle - Dematerialization</i>	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies reduced mass or material types in the product or its packaging.	EI	greencirclecertified.com
GreenPla	X	X	X	X	No active website found.	EI	n.a
Healthy Child Healthy World	N	X	X	X	Not an ecolabel but an organization focused on protecting children from harmful chemicals and promoting safer, healthier environments.	EI	healthychild.org
Hong Kong Ecolabel	X	X	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	hkfep.com
Hong Kong Green Label (HKGLS)	Y	Y	Y	N	A Hongkong/Chinese national ecolabel.	EI	greencouncil.org
IMO Certified	X	Y	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	ecocert.com
Korean Ecolabel	Y	Y	Y	N	Ecolabel likely not used in the U.K or within EU.	EI	keiti.re.kr
Label STEP	Y	Y	N	N	Certifies hand-made carpets.	EI	label-step.org
MAS Certified Green	Y	Y	N	N	Certifies interior construction products and furniture.	EI	mascertifiedgreen.com
Max Havelaar	X	X	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	fairtrademaxhavelaar.ch
Migros ECO	X	X	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	migros.ch
Milieukeur: the Dutch environmental quality label	Y	Y	N	N	A Dutch national ecolabel.	EI	milieukeur.nl
NATURTEXTIL Best	X	X	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	naturtextil.de
NSF Sustainability Certified Product	Y	Y	N	N	Certifies the following sectors, Food and beverage, water systems, nutrition, transportation.	EI	nsf.org
NSF/ANSI 140 Sustainability Assessment for Carpet	Y	Y	N	X	Certifies carpets.	EI	carpet-rug.org
NSF/ANSI 336: Sustainability Assessment for Commercial Furnishings Fabric	Y	Y	N	X	Certifies furnishing textiles.	EI	contracttextiles.org
National Programme of Environmental	X	Y	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	sazp.sk

Assessment and Ecolabelling in the Slovak Republik (NPEHOV)							
Naturland e.V.	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifies organic fibres.	EI naturland.de
Nike Considered Design	Y	Y	N	X		Certifies shoes.	EI investors.nike.com
Nordic Ecolabel or "Swan"	Y	Y	Y	N		ISO Type I.	EI nordic-swan-ecolabel.org
OE-100 & OE-Blended	X	X	X	X		Textile Exchange ccolabels that are phased out and replaced by Organic Content Standard.	EI n.a
OK biobased	Y	Y	N	N		Certifies products made from renewable raw materials, no textile fashion products certified.	EI tuv-at.be
Oeko-Tex Standard 100	X	Y	OE	X		An organisation, six ecolabels below listed separately.	EI oeko-tex.com
<i>Oeko-Tex Standard 101 - Made in Green</i>	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifies wet chemical processes after the product has been 'Made in Green' and 'Standard 100' certified, and sewn at 'STeP' certified production units.	EI oeko-tex.com
<i>Oeko-Tex Standard 102 - Standard 100</i>	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifies textiles from fibre stage to finished composite consumer products.	EI oeko-tex.com
<i>Oeko-Tex Standard 103 - Organic Cotton</i>	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifies organic cotton.	EI oeko-tex.com
<i>Oeko-Tex Standard 104 - STeP</i>	Y	Y	Y	N		Textile production certification (not products).	EI oeko-tex.com
<i>Oeko-Tex Standard 105 - Eco Passport</i>	Y	Y	Y	N		Product certification of paints and chemicals used in the textile industry.	EI oeko-tex.com
<i>Oeko-Tex Standard 106 - Responsible Business</i>	N	Y	Y	N		A certificate not an ecolabel.	EI oeko-tex.com
Oregon Tilth	Y	Y	N	N		Certifies organic agriculture but refers to GOTS for certifying cotton.	EI tilth.org
Organic Farmers & Growers Certification	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifies organic production and processing in the UK.	EI ofgorganic.org
Processed Chlorine Free	Y	Y	N	X		Certifies paper products indicating no-use of chlorine or chlorine derivatives.	EI intengine.com
SCS Sustainable Choice	X	Y	Or g	X		Ecolabel no longer active.	EI n.a
<i>Recycled Claim Standard</i>	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifies that a product contains at least 5% recycled material.	EI scsglobalservices.com
<i>Responsible Wool Standard</i>	Y	Y	Y	N		Certification for wool farmers and sellers that aims to improve the welfare of sheep and the land they graze on.	EI scsglobalservices.com
<i>Sustainable Fabric Certification</i>	Y	Y	N	X		Certifies commercial furnishings fabric.	EI scsglobalservices.com
SMaRT Consensus Sustainable Product Standards	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifies building materials, fabric, apparel, textile & flooring.	EI mts.sustainableproducts.com
SEE What You Are Buying Into	X	N	X	X		No active website found.	EI n.a
Singapore Green Label Scheme (SGLS)	Y	Y	Y	N		Ecolabel for products sold on the Malasian market.	EI sec.org.sg
Skal Eko Symbol	X	Y	X	X		Website not available in English.	EI skal.nl
Soil Association Organic Standard	Y	Y	Y	N		Certifes that organic farmers, processors, and retailers adhere to organic regulations.	EI soilassociation.org
Sourcemap	N	X	X	X		Not an ecolabel but a platform and software service that provides tools for supply chain mapping, transparency, and sustainability tracking.	EI sourcemap.com
SustentaX	X	X	X	X		No active website found.	EI n.a
TerraCycle	N	X	X	X		Not an ecolabel, focus on waste management and recycling, not on certifying products.	EI terracycle.com

Texas Certified Organically Produced	Y	Y	Y	N	A U.S national ecolabel.	EI	texasagriculture.gov
Thai Green Label	Y	Y	N	X	Does not certify textile fashion.	EI	tei.or.th/greenlabel
Timberland Green Index	X	X	X	X	Ecolabel no longer active.	EI	n.a
Totally Chlorine Free	Y	Y	N	X	Certifies chlorine free virgin fiber paper.	EI	n.a
Tunisia Ecolabel	X	Y	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	citet.nat.tn
UL Environment Multi-Attribute Certification	Y	Y	N	X	Does not certify textile fashion.	EI	ul.com
USDA Certified BioBased	Y	Y	Y	N	Only certifies that at least 25% of the product is made from biobased materials.	EI	biopreferred.gov
WindMade	X	N	X	X	No active website found.	EI	n.a
ZQ Natural Fibre	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies wool.	EI	discoverzq.com
bluesign® standard	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies chemicals used in denim.	EI	bluesign.com
eco-INSTITUT-Label	Y	Y	N	X	Certifies bedding goods, mattresses and furnitures.	EI	eco-institut-label.de
ÖkoControl	X	X	X	X	Website not available in English.	EI	oekocontrol.com
Ø-label: Norway	Y	Y	N	N	A Norwegian national ecolabel.	EI	debio.no
Solidaridad	Y	Y	Y	Y	Certifies equality and workers conditions.	FU	solidaridadnetwork.org
Cascale (former Sustainable Apparel Coalition)	N	X	X	X	Not an ecolabel but a platform for TF manufacturers, brands, and retailers.	FU	cascale.org
Sane Standard	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies textile fashion final products.	FU	sane-standard.com
Woolmark	N	Y	Y	N	Not an ecolabel but an organisation that conducts research, development and marketing along the worldwide supply chain for Australian wool.	FU	wool.com
Canopy	N	Y	Y	N	Not a certification or ecolabel but an advocacy and partnership initiative focus on influencing corporate behavior and supply chain practices rather than certifying individual products.	FU	canopyplanet.org
Forest Stewardship Council	Y	Y	N	N	Certifies forest management.	FU	fsc.org
Made Safe	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies screening of harmful substances in final products.	FU	madesafe.org
Organic cotton Accelerator (OCA)	N	X	X	X	Not an ecolabel but an organisation focused on promoting organic and sustainable agriculture.	FU	organiccottonaccelerator.org
Regenerative Organic Certified	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies organic fibers.	FU	regenorganic.org
USDA Organic	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies a product has at least 70% certified organic content.	FU	usda.gov
Fur Free Retailer	N	Y	Y	Y	Not an ecolabel but a certification for fur-free content.	FU	furfreeretailer.com
PETA	N	Y	Y	Y	Not an ecolabel but an animal rights organisation.	FU	peta.org
Cotton Made in Africa	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies organic cotton.	FU	cottonmadeinafrica.org
Ethical Trading Initiative	N	X	X	X	Not an ecolabel but a platform for members.	FU	ethicaltrade.org
Social Accountability International - SAI	N	Y	Y	Y	A social standard certification.	FU	sa-intl.org
Social Accountability Accreditation Services	N	Y	Y	Y	A social standard certification.	FU	sa-intl.org
Worldwide Responsible Accredited Production - WRAP	Y	Y	Y	Y	Certifies social compliance standards.	FU	wrapcompliance.org
Fair Wear Foundation - FWF	N	Y	Y	Y	Not an ecolabel but an initiative for human rights due diligence across the industry.	FU	fairwear.org

World Fair Trade Organization (WFTO)	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies the entire organization based on adherence to broad fair trade principles.	FU	wfto.com
Clean Clothes Campaign	N	Y	Y	N	Not an ecolabel but network dedicated to improving working conditions and empowering workers in the global garment and sportswear industries.	FU	cleanclothes.org
FabScrap	N	Y	Y	N	Not an ecolabel but a charitable organisation for recycling and reuse of textiles.	FU	fairforlife.org
Fashion for Good	N	Y	Y	N	Not an ecolabel but a global sustainable fashion initiative.	FU	fashionforgood.com
Global Fashion Agenda (GFA)	N	Y	Y	N	Not an ecolabel but an organisation that fosters industry collaboration on sustainability in fashion to accelerate impact.	FU	globalfashionagenda.org
Green Story	N	Y	Y	N	Not an ecolabel but a platform for LCA assessments.	FU	greenstory.ca
Eco Choice Aotearoa	Y	Y	Y	N	A New Zealand national ecolabel.	EGA	ecochoiceaotearoa.org.nz
Green Mark Taiwan	Y	X	X	X	No active website found.	EGA	n.a
Green Product Mark	Y	Y	N	X	Does not certify textile fashion.	EGA	uv.com
Ecocert	N	Y	X	X	Not an ecolabel itself but a certification body.	EGA	ecocert.com
ICEA	Y	Y	N	X	An Italian national ecolabel.	EGA	icea.bio
NATURTEXTIL	Y	X	X	X	Website not available in English.	EGA	naturtextil.de
Rainforest Alliance	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies sustainable farming.	EGA	rainforest-alliance.org
Vegan	N	Y	X	X	Not an ecolabel but an organisation that has a certification 'Vegan Trademark'.	EGA	vegansociety.com
Der Grüne Punkt	N	Y	X	X	Not an ecolabel but a licensing symbol used primarily within EU to indicate that the producer of a product has made a financial contribution to a national packaging recovery organization.	EGA	gruener-punkt.de
Green Button (Grüner Knopf)	Y	Y	Y	N	Certifies textile fashion final products.	UKF T	gruener-knopf.de

Source: Authors